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Bibliography

Primary Sources

Álǫgrip Af Noǫregskonungasgum: A Twelfth-Century Synoptic History of the Kings of Norway, ed. and trans. M. J. Driscoll (London, 2008).

Alberic of Trois-Fontaines, *Chronica Albrici monachi Trium Fontium, a monacho novi monasterii Hoiensis interpolata*, MGH SS, xxiii, 826

Albert of Aachen, *Historia Ierosolimitana: History of the Journey to Jerusalem*, ed. and trans. S.B. Edgington (Oxford, 2007), 798.

Morkinskinna: The Earliest Icelandic Chronicle of the Norwegian Kings, 1030-1157, ed. and trans. T. M. Andersson (New York, 2000), 313-59.

Archives historiques du Poitou, xxii, 14–16.

Aubri of Trois-Fontaines, *Chronicon*, ed. P. Scheffer-Boichorst, MGH SS, xxiii, 631–950, at 855, ll. 36–8

Bernard of Clairvaux, *Opera*, ed. J. Leclercq, H. Rochais and C. H. Talbot, 8 vols (Rome, 1957–77), vii, 85–6 no. 31

Cartulaire Noire de la cathédrale d'Angers, ed. C. Urseau (Paris, 1908), 166 no. 89; *ibid.*, 358 no. 235.

Cartulaires de Molesmes, ancien diocèse de Langres (916–1250), ed. J. Laurent, 2 vols (Paris, 1907–11), ii, 321–3 no. 173.

The Cartulary of Montier-en-Der, 666–1129, ed. C. B. Bouchard (Toronto, 2004), 287–9 no. 146.

Cartularium monasterii beatae Mariae Caritatis Andegavensis, in Archives d'Anjou 3. Angers, Cosnier et Lachèse, ed. P. Marchegay (Angers, 1854), 215–17.

Châlons-en-Champagne, Archives Départementales de la Marne, MS H 737.

Charters of the Earldom of Hereford, ed. D. Walker, Camden Miscellany 22 (1964), 56 no. 94.

Chartes de Saint-Julien de Tours, ed. L.-J. Denis (Le Mans, 1912–13), i, 87 no. 67.

Chartes de Terre Sainte provenant de l'abbaye de Notre Dame de Josaphat, ed. H.-F. Delaborde (Paris, 1880), 44 no. 17

Collection des principaux cartulaires du diocèse de Troyes, ed. C. Lalore, 7 vols (Paris, 1875–90), vii, 23–31 no. 18

[Database of Crusaders to the Holy Land, 1095-1149](http://www.hrionline.ac.uk/crusaders/) (<http://www.hrionline.ac.uk/crusaders/>)

De oorkonden der graven van Vlaanderen Juli 1128–September 1191 Uitgave II. Bd. 1, Regering van Diederik van de Elzas (Juli 1128–17 Januari 1168), ed. T. de Hemptinne and A. Verhulst (Brussels, 1988), 88 no. 50

Epernay et l'abbaye de Saint-Martin de cette ville, ed. A. Nicaise, 2 vols (Châlons-sur-Marne, 1869), ii, 118 no. 3.

Ekkehard of Aura, *Chronicon universale*, ed. G. Waitz, MGH SS, vi, 262, ll. 5–9.

Fagriskinna: a catalogue of the kings of Norway, ed. and trans. A. Finlay (Leiden, 2003), 74-5.

Fulcher of Chartres, *Historia Hierosolymitana*, ed. H. Hagenmayer (Heidelberg, 1913), 544.

Ibn al-AthÄ«r, *The Chronicle of Ibn al-AthÄ«r for the Crusading Period from al-Kamil fi'l-Ta'rikh. Part 1: The Years 491-541/1097/1146: The Coming of the Franks and the Muslim Response*, trans. D. S. Richards (Farnham, 2005), 152.

Ibn al-QalÄ«nisÄ«, *The Damascus Chronicle of the Crusades*, trans. H. A. R. Gibb (London, 1932), 106.

Laurence of Liège, *Gesta episcoporum Virdunensium et abbatum sancti Vitoni*, ed. G. Waitz, MGH SS, x, 504

H. E. Mayer, ed., *Die Urkunden der lateinischen Könige von Jerusalem*, 4 vols. (Hannover, 2010), 1:272 no. 111, 275 no. 115.

Orderic Vitalis, *The Ecclesiastical History of Orderic Vitalis*, ed. and trans. M. Chibnall, 6 vols. (Oxford, 1969-80), vi, 514 and n. 4; 275 no. 173 and 289 no. 184; 404 no. 254 and 405–6 no. 255.

PL, clxii, 251–2 no. 245.

Paul Riant, *Expéditions et pèlerinages des scandinaves en Terre Sainte au temps des croisades* (Paris, 1865), 179

Steven Runciman, *A History of the Crusades*, 3 vols (Cambridge, 1952), ii, 92

Snorri Sturluson, *Heimskringla: History of the Kings of Norway*, trans. L.M. Hollander (Austin, 1967), 688-714.

Theodoricus Monachus, *Historia de antiquitate regum Norwagiensium*, in *Monumenta historica Norvegiæ*, ed. Gustav Storm (Christiania, 1880).

William of Malmesbury, *Gesta Regum Anglorum: The History of the English Kings*, ed. R. A. B. Mynors, with R. M. Thomson and M. Winterbottom, 2 vols (Oxford, 1998–99), 1: 480–81.

WT, 633.

Secondary Sources

- Adair, Penelope A. "The Flemish Comital Family and the Crusades," in *The Crusades: Other Experiences, Alternate Perspectives*, ed. Khalil I Semaan (Binghamton, 2003), pp. 101-112, esp. p. 108
- Bur, M., *La formation du comté de Champagne v.950–v.1150* (Nancy, 1977), 259–78
- Doxey, G. B., 'Norwegian Crusaders and the Balearic Islands', *Scandinavian Studies*, 68/2 (1996), 139-60;
- Evergate, Theodore, *Henry the Liberal: Count of Champagne, 1127–1181* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2016)
- de Hemptinne Thérèse, "Les épouses de croisés et pèlerins flamands au xie et xiie siècle: L'exemple des comtesses de Flandre Clémence et Sibylle," in *Autour de la première croisade: Actes du Colloque de la Society for the Study of the Crusades and the Latin East* (Clermont-Ferrand, 22–25 juin 1995), ed. Michel Balard (Clermont-Ferrand, 1996), pp. 83–95.
- Hurlock, K., *Wales and the Crusades, 1095–1291* (Cardiff, 2011), 75.
- Jakobsson, A., 'Image is Everything: The Morkinskinna Account of King Sigurðr of Norway's Journey to the Holy Land', *Parergon* 30/1 (2013), 121-40.
- LoPrete, K. A., *Adela of Blois: Countess and Lord (c.1067–1137)* (Dublin, 2007).
- Loud, G. A., 'Some Reflections on the Failure of the Second Crusade', *Crusades* 4 (2005): 1–14, at 4–5.
- Nicholas, David, *Medieval Flanders* (New York, 1992), pp. 70-1.
- Norako, L. K., 'Crusading Gone Global? The Icelandic Magnussona Saga's Visions of the World and Home', *Literature Compass* 11/7 (2014), 423-34.
- Paul, Nicholas, *To Follow in Their Footsteps: the Crusades and Family Memory in the High Middle Ages* (Ithaca, 2012), 39-47.
- Phillips, J., *Defenders of the Holy Land: Relations Between the Latin East and the West, 1119–1187* (Oxford, 1996), 129 and 271–81.
- Riley-Smith, J., *The First Crusaders, 1095–1131* (Cambridge, 1997), 242–3.
- Walker, David, 'A Letter from the Holy Land', *The English Historical Review* 72/285 (1957), 662–5, at 665.
- West, C., 'Count Hugh of Troyes and the Territorial Principality in Early Twelfth-Century Europe', *English Historical Review* 127/526 (2012): 523–48.

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